

A REVIEW STUDY ON PATHOGENESIS OF COVID-19 AND EFFECTIVE MEDICINAL PLANTS

Rajesh Kumar*¹, Akash Parmar*²

*^{1,2}Research Pharmacy, Parul Institute of Management & Research, Faculty of
Management Studies, Parul University, Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

E mail: rajmathuriya360@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Several corona viruses including SARS-CoV, MERS-CoV, and SARS-CoV-2, causes serious infections from the last couple of decades claiming the death of people all over the world. In which SARS CoV-2 which causes COVID-19, is a serious and one of the major pandemic in human history. Understanding the pathogenesis of any disease it is easy to find an effective cure for that disease. Natural products have always played a crucial role in the drug development process against various viral infectious diseases. Ayurvedic medicinal plants used in treatment of various diseases from ancient age. Due to lack of research in Ayurvedic and as well as in herbal fields it is very challenging to find a better and effective natural herb and derivative to treat the various diseases effectively. This article contains a brief summarized introduction of COVID-19 and details of Medicinal plants which can be effective in the current situation of COVID-19, which are extracted from various scientific studies and Ayurvedic considerations.

Keywords: coronavirus, COVID-19, SARS, MERS, SARS-CoV2, medicinal plants, Ayurveda, treatment, natural herbs, viral infectious diseases.

I. INTRODUCTION

As we know SARS CoV-2, also known as Coronavirus is a source of coronavirus infectious disease (COVID-19). This is considered as fetal disease and spread rapidly human to human. This viral disease was announced as a pandemic, people all over the world affected by this. Coronavirus is one of the major viruses which primarily target the human respiratory system. Before this pandemic, corona viruses were also responsible for two other epidemic diseases, severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) by SARS-CoV in 2002 and the Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) by MERS-CoV in 2012. In December 2019 a large number of patients were admitted to the hospital having pneumonia and other symptoms with respiratory problems of an unknown etiology which can rapidly spread between people. On 30 January 2020, total 7734 cases of the new coronavirus were reported in China and 90 other cases reported from a number of countries including Taiwan, Thailand, Vietnam, Malaysia, Nepal, Japan UAE, USA, India, Germany, France etc which showed a rapid spread of the disease. On 11 March 2020 WHO declared COVID-19 as a pandemic, showing 1,18,000 cases in 110 countries and territories around the world. The outbreak of SARS-CoV2 was considered to have a zoonotic transmission associated with the seafood market in Wuhan city, China. Later it was recognized that human to human transmission played a major role in further outbreak. This virus is easily and rapidly transmittable between human and caused pandemic disease worldwide. Due to lack of medicine and vaccine of this disease a large number of deaths continue to rise and most countries declared full lockdown and social distancing. Several studies showed that the elder patients or patients suffering from any other diseases (e.g. hypertension, diabetes, asthma etc) are more susceptible and have a low recovery rate compared to children. Virus can be present everywhere in the world. Our immune system always fights against each and every pathogen (when they enter into the body) present in the global village. But in most cases our immune system can protect us from the pathogen due to various reasons. Ayurveda has lots of medicinal herbs which can boost up your immune system to fight against pathogenic microbes. In human civilization before the allopathic system of medicine everyone depends on natural plants for health concerns. The Indian traditional system of medicine is known as Ayurveda (Science of Life), which is derived from Rigveda and Atharvaveda.

Petrovska et al.(2012), described in his article about the Historical usage of medicinal plants in human civilization. Due to lack of research, study, interest and powerful impact of allopathy the Ayurvedic knowledge is slowly-slowly disappearing. Ayurveda claims the treatment of every disease by the herbal plant. Here we study some medicinal plants which are effective in various viral diseases which can be developed as treatment for COVID-19. Some of them have been studied by various scientists and proven to have effective ingredients to treat the COVID-19. (1,2,3,4,5)

II. SYMPTOMS

Coronavirus can easily transmit through body fluids, contact, sneezing and air droplets having coronavirus. The symptoms of coronavirus infection appear after the incubation period of 2-5 days which can vary patient to patient and on their health and status of immune system. The most common symptoms that appear on onset of illness are mild fever, cough with throat irritation, chill, loss of taste, fatigue and muscle pain. Other symptoms include sputum production, headache, haemoptysis, diarrhea and dyspnoea. While severe infection includes symptoms loss of smell, difficulties in breathing, shortness in breath, loss of speech and severe problems. Clinical features by a chest CT scan or x ray presented pneumonia. However symptoms may vary patient to patient depending upon the status of the immune system and other disease state. A patient suffering from diabetes can show different symptoms in corona virus infection in comparison to a patient who does not have any previous disease or disorder. A large number of patients infected from coronavirus having no symptoms at an early stage.(6,7)

Symptoms of COVID-19

III. PATHOGENESIS

Patients infected with COVID-19 showed higher leukocyte numbers and increased levels of plasma pro-inflammatory cytokines. Corona viruses are enveloped, single-stranded RNA viruses of 30 kb size. They mainly belong to 4 genera: α , β , γ , and δ ; from which α and β corona viruses infect only mammals.

Pathogenesis of COVID-19 can be easily understood by following points:

1. When coronavirus (SARS CoV-2) enters the host body it is attached with ACE-2 receptors similar to SARS CoV) present on cell surfaces in the heart, lungs, kidney, mucosa and others. Pneumocyte type 2 cells (present in alveoli) having ACE-2 receptors in abundant quantity. So let we consider pneumocyte type 2 cells of alveoli as reference.
2. Corona virus attached with ACE-2 receptors of pneumocyte-2 with the help of spike proteins and insert viral genome i.e. SS RNA into the host cell. This SS RNA attached with Ribosome of host cell and start translating to form several viral polyproteins which are converted in non structural proteins by the protease enzyme and finally with the help of Endoplasmic reticulum of the host cell it converted in specific viral proteins e.g. spike proteins.
3. Similarly RNA dependent RNA polymerase makes copies of the viral RNA. New viral RNA and viral

proteins form together with the help of packaging and processing functions of the Golgi body.

4. After synthesis of new corona viruses they are removed from the cell by exocytosis inside secretory vesicles and by bursting the surface of the infected cell. Finally it causes damage of pneumocytes-2 which causes initiation of inflammatory response.
5. Damaged cells (pneumocyte-2) released interferon and cytokines which are recognized by alveolar macrophages. Interferons and cytokines stimulate surrounding nerves endings which resulted in dry cough (first symptom). Macrophages further secretes TNF- α , IL 1 & IL 6 in blood circulation which increase the permeability of alveolar capillaries which release the capillaries fluid into interstitial space cause interstitial edema and when this fluid enters in alveoli causes alveolar edema and increase the fluid causes pneumonia.
6. TNF- α and ILs circulating in the blood stimulate the hypothalamus to increase the body temperature (Fever).
7. Chemical factors TNF- α , ILs attract the blood circulating neutrophils and monocytes and transfer them into alveoli. These monocytes and neutrophils remove out cell debris and kill the viruses and secrete the toxic by product i.e. reactive oxygen species or free oxygen radicals. These reactive oxygen byproducts damage the healthy alveolar cells.
8. More release of capillary fluid causes pneumonia like symptoms.
9. Damage of pneumocyte-2 causes decrease in release of surfactant which results in alveolar collapse which resulted in difficulties in breathing and exchange of gases, decrease in oxygen concentration in systemic circulation.
10. Due to decrease in oxygen concentrations, the heart starts to pump fast to fulfill the oxygen demand of the body and also several tissue damages occur which causes failure of organs e.g. liver, kidney etc.(6,8,9,10,11)

Cellular life cycle of SARS CoV-2

IV. DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICINE ACCORDING TO ABOVE PATHOGENESIS

There is no specific medicine or vaccine to treat COVID-19 till now. Every country is trying to discover the effective way to treat this disease. There the following strategies which can be used for developing effective treatment:

1. Destroying the spike proteins of the virus.
2. Inhibition of attachment of ACE-2 with spike proteins.
3. Preparing monoclonal antibodies against viruses.
4. Inhibition of translation process of viral RNA.
5. Inhibition of RNA dependent RNA polymerase.
6. Inhibition of attachment of host ribosome with viral genome.

V. MEDICINAL PLANTS

Here are some medicinal plants which can help in controlling the corona virus disease by various ways e.g. boosting the immune system.

Medicinal Plants	Chemical Ingredients	Uses	Researches
Holy Basil (Ocimum sanctum)	Eugenol , carvacrol, caryophyllene, linalool, germacrene, oleanolic acid	Bronchitis, malaria, diarrhea, eye & skin diseases, insect bites, immunity booster , Dysentery, viral protection .	Mondal S et al.(2011) proved in their research work that Tulsinol (A, B, C, D, E, F, & G) and dihydroeugenol B which are found in Holy Basil inhibits SARS coronavirus main protease and papain like protease.(12,13)
Ashwagandh a or Indian ginseng (Withania somnifera)	Withanolide, Withaferin A, ergostane and cuscohygrine.	Immunity booster, viral infection , cough and cold, fever, anxiety, depression, antioxidant, improve reproductive health	A research conducted by the scientist at IIT-Delhi has found that ashwagandha contains certain bio-actives that interact with SARS CoV 2, withanone Obtained from ashwagandha can block the replication process of the novel coronavirus.
			Chandel V et al. (2020) studied as Withanolide D & Warfarin A most suitable inhibitors against 3C like main protease (3CL pro) of coronavirus.(13,14)
Giloy or Guduchi (Tinospora cordifolia)	Furanolactone, Tinosporide, giloinin, gelonin sitosterol, clerodane, tinosporin and b-sitosol.	Anti-diabetic, anti-malarial, antioxidant, immunomodulatory , anti-neoplastic, Anti-allergic and anti-stress. Used in various Ayurvedic preparations.	Is being under research by various scientists. It has proven to increase immunity.

Yastimadhu or Liquorice (Glycyrrhiza glabra)	Glycyrrhizin, glycyrrhizic acid, enoxolone, glabridin, liquiritin, liquiritigenin & liqco-coumarine.	Immunity booster , anti-allergic, peptic ulcer, anti-inflammatory & Respiratory infections.	Bailly et al.(2020) described in his research article the Effectiveness of Glycyrrhizin in COVID-19 & the associated respiratory syndrome.(15)
Amla or Indian gooseberry (Emblica officinalis)	Gallic acid, Ascorbic acid (vitamin E), Chebulic acid, chebulagic acid, emblicanin A & B, ellagic acid, ellagitannins and glucogallin.	Immunity booster , skin disorders, respiratory infection, dysentery, protects cells against free radical damage and antioxidant.	It has proven to be effective in IBV (infectious bronchitis virus: a type of coronavirus) and other viral diseases. Wu C et al. (2020), described in their research article that phyllaemblicin-B and Phyllaemblinol have high binding affinity to helicase protein and Phyllaemblicin G7 has binding affinity with spike proteins of SARS-CoV2.(13,16)
Pippali or Indian long pepper (Piper longum)	Piperettine, chavicine, coumaperine, methoxyphenyl, pyrrolidine, eugenol	Respiratory disorder, asthma, bronchitis, headache, toothache, cholera, comma, cough, worms and immunity enhancer.	According to the Ministry of Ayush India, use of long pepper in kwath (kadha) preparation increases immunity and protects against SARS CoV-2 and other viral diseases. Gonzalez et al.(2020), described that Piperine strongly binding to 3CL-protease of COVID-19 in comparison to the antimalarial drugs.(17)
Garlic (Allium sativum)	Allicin, allin, ajoene, cysteine, alliinase, diallyl sulfide etc.	Aphrodisiacs, increase immunity , viral infection, heart and other circulatory diseases, worms, cold, cough and mild irritation.	Mohajer Shojai et al.(2016) proved that garlic is effective against IBV (infectious bronchitis virus).(18)
Artemisia annua	Artemisinin I, II, III, IV & V, artemisinic acid, artemisia lactone, artemisinin, exoxyarteannuic acid, stigmaterol, artemetrin, friedelin & quercetagetin.	Malaria, fever, inflammation, antifungal, antiviral, antibacterial, antitumor, antioxidant, antileishmanial and respiratory disorders.	Haq F.U. et al.(2020), described the various aspects about Artemisia in article : Artemisia annua : trials are needed for COVID-19, and described various aspects that can be used in COVID-19 for effective treatment.(19)

Turmeric (<i>Curcuma longa</i>)	Curcumin, demethoxycurcumin and bisdemethoxycurcumin, Curcuminoids	Anti Inflammatory, antibacterial, antiviral, immunity booster, irritation, skin infection, respiratory problems, swelling, pain relief etc.	Gonzalez et al.(2020), described in his research that Curcumin strongly binds to 3C-like main protease (3CL-protease) of COVID-19 in comparison with antimalarial drugs.(13,17)
--------------------------------------	---	--	--

Basu A. et al.(2020), studied various natural compounds for inhibition of binding of spike protein with the ACE-2 receptors and published his research article titled Computational approach for the design of potential spike protein binding natural compounds in SARS-CoV2. In this article they described some medicinal compounds: hesperidin, emodin, rhein and chrysin and found effective against SARS-CoV2.(20) A brief summary of this article as follows:

- 1. Hesperidin:** Hesperidin interacts with amino acids of spike protein fragments of virus and inhibits it from attaching with ACE-2 receptors. Hesperidin is widely found in various plants e.g. Citrus fruits, Citrus limon, Hyssopus officinalis, Barosma betulina, peppermint etc.
- 2. Emodin :** Acting same as hesperidin. It is found in Rheum emodi, Rheum sp., Fallopia japonica, Aloe vera, senna, cassia, Rhubarb.
- 3. Rhein:** Also known as cassia acid. Act same as emodin and hesperidin. Found in Rhubarb, Rheum palmatum, Cassia reticulata etc.
- 4. Chrysin:** capable of inhibiting the growth and replication of viruses. Generally found in Oroxylum indicum.

VI. CONCLUSION

The pandemic by COVID-19 is a measure current issue affecting people worldwide. Above article is the summarized and brief extract of pathogenesis obtained by various scientific studies till now which is described in the easiest way. Without proper fundamental investigation of pathogenesis it is impossible to find an effective way to treat this disease. There is an urgent need to develop targeted therapies to control this pandemic. To discover effective therapy it is important to study exact pathogenesis of the virus which is under investigated. Medicinal plants have been used in treatment of various diseases since ancient times. Due to lack of research medicinal properties of most medicinal herbal plants are still unknown. Above article is a collection of some medicinal plants that may have effective therapeutic properties against SARS-CoV2 obtained from various research articles and described here in summarized way.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to acknowledge Parul University and respected faculties to support toward the completion of this review paper and also acknowledge all the authors whose research works help a lot to complete this article.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] Singhal T. (2020). A Review of Coronavirus Disease-2019 (COVID-19). The Indian Journal of Pediatric, page no. 281-286.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12098-020-03263-6>
- [2] Petrosillo N., Viceconte G., Ergonul O., Ippolito G. & Petersen E. (2020). COVID-19, SARS and MERS: are they closely related. Clinical Microbiological and Infection, June 2020, 26(6), pages 729-734.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2020.03.026>
- [3] Zu Z. Y, Jiang M. D., Xu P. P., Chen W., Ni Q. Q., Lu G. M., & Zhang L. J. (2020); Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) : A Perspective from China. Radiology, Vol. 296, No.2, .
<https://doi.org/10.1148/radiol.2020200490>

- [4] Petrovska B.B. (2012). Historical review of medicinal plants usage. in *Pharmacological Reviews*, page no. 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0973-7847.95849>
- [5] Jaiswal Y. S. & Williams L. L. (Jan 2017). A glimpse of Ayurveda - The forgotten history and principles of Indian traditional medicines. *Journal of Traditional and Complementary Medicine*, volume 7, issue 1, pages 50-53.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtcme.2016.02.002>
- [6] Hafeez A., Ahmad S., Siddiqui S. A., Ahmad M. & Mishra S. (2020). A Review of COVID-19 (Coronavirus Disease-2019) Diagnosis, Treatment and Prevention. *Eurasian Journal of Medicine and Oncology*, Vol.4, Issue 3, pages: 116-125. <https://doi.org/10.14744/ejmo.2020.90,853>
- [7] Cascella M., Rajnik M., Cuomo A., Dulebohn S. C., & Napoli R. D. (2020). Features, Evaluation and Treatment Coronavirus (COVID-19). *StatPearls*. StatPearls Publishing. NBK554776
- [8] Mason R. J. (2020). Pathogenesis of COVID-19 from a cell biology perspective. *European Respiratory Journal*, Vol. 55 no. 4.
<https://doi.org/10.1183/13993003.00607-2020>
- [9] Shoenfeld Y. (2020). Corona (COVID-19) time musing: Our involvement in COVID-19 pathogenesis, diagnosis, treatment and vaccine planning. *Autoimmune Review*, Vol. 19, issue 6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autrev.2020.102538>
- [10] Rothan H. A. & Byrareddy S. N. (2020). The epidemiology and pathogenesis of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) outbreak. *Journal of Autoimmunity*, Vol. 109, Elsevier Publishers.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaut.2020.102433>
- [11] Duan G., Jin Y., Yang H., Ji W., Wu W., Chen S. & Zhang W. (2020) *Virology, Epidemiology, Pathogenesis and Control of COVID-19*. *Viruses*, 12(4), page no. 372. <https://doi.org/10.3390/v12040372>
- [12] Mondal S., Varma S., Bamola V. D., Naik S. N., Mirdha B. R., Padhi M. M., Mehta N., & Mahapatra S. C. (2011). Double-blinded randomized controlled trial for immunomodulatory effects of Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum* Linn.) leaf extract on healthy volunteers. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*, 136(3), page no. 452-456. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2011.05.012>
- [13] Brahmabhatt R. V. (2020). Herbal medicines in management and prevention of COVID-19. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, Vol. 9, issue 3, page no. 1221-1223.
- [14] Chandel V., Raj S. & Rathi B. (2020). In silico Identification of Potent COVID-19 Main Protease Inhibitors from FDA Approved Antiviral Compounds and Phytochemicals through Molecular Docking: A Drug Repurposing Approach. Preprints, Version 1. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202003.0349.v1>
- [15] Bailly C. & Verboten G. (2020). Glycyrrhizin: An alternative drug for the treatment of COVID-19 infection and the associated respiratory syndrome?. *Pharmacology and Therapeutics*, Volume 214, 107618. Elsevier Publishers. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pharmthera.2020.107618>
- [16] Wu C, Liu Y., Yang Y., Zhang P., Zhong W. & Wang Y., Wand Q., Xu Y., Li M., Li X., Zheng M., Chen L. & Li H. (2020). Analysis of therapeutic targets for SARS-CoV-2 and discovery of potential drugs by computational methods. *Acta Pharmaceutica Sinica B*, vol. 10, issue 5, pages 766-788. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsb.2020.02.008>
- [17] Gonzalez-Paz L. A., Lossada C. A. & Moncayo L. S. (2020). Theoretical Molecular Docking Study of the Structural Disruption of the Viral 3CL-Protease of COVID-19 Induced by Binding of Capsaicin, Piperine and Curcumin Part 1: A Comparative Study with Chloroquine and Hydrochloroquine Two Antimalarial drugs. *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-21206/v1>
- [18] Mohajer Shojai T., Ghalyanchi Langeroudi A., Karimi V., Barin A. & Sadri N. (2016). The effect of *Allium sativum* (Garlic) extract on infectious bronchitis virus in specific pathogen free embryonic egg. *Avicenna journal of phytomedicine*, 6(4), page no. 458-267.

- [19] Haq F. U., Roman M., Ahmad K., Rahman S. U., Shah S. M. A., Suleman N., Ullah S., Ahmad I. & Ullah W. (2020). Artemisia annua: Trails are needed for COVID-19. *Phytotherapy Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ptr.6733>
- [20] Basu A., Sarkar A. & Maulik U. (2020). Computational approach for the design of potential spike protein binding natural compounds in SARS-CoV2. *Pharmacodynamics*, Research Square. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-33181/v1>